

RESEARCH ON IDENTIFYING THE DEFICIENCIES OF THE EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION PROCESS IN THE PRE-UNIVERSITY EDUCATION SYSTEM AND THE INFLUENCE OF THE PANDEMIC CONTEXT

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Abstract

Purpose – This paper considers the importance of external communication at the level of pre-university education institutions in Romania and aims to identify the aspects that disrupt the external communication process of educational institutions, on the one hand, and the aspects that have influenced the communication process during the pandemic and its consequences, on the other hand.

Methodology/Approach - The sampling method chosen was random sampling combined with purposive sampling for respondents from pre-university educational institutions. The questionnaire was applied to teachers in pre-university education.

Findings – The findings of this study revealed that the school formally establishes its communication relationship with its partners, but teachers are not specifically trained by the school through training programs. On the other hand, a problem of pressing topicality and complexity was not only the communication between the school and the higher institutions, but also that with the family or the community during the exceptional situation established in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Research limitations/implications – The limitations of this research come from the fact that the answers collected are only from teachers whereas the family or community members' opinions are not captured.

Practical implications – These conclusions show that the school is the one that must reach an understanding of the different environments, experiences, values, cultures, religions and other factors that could affect the communication relationship with the family and the community. It is clear that the school staff also need communication skills for effective communication. The communication channel must be modern, efficient and as personal as possible.

Originality/value – The conclusions and recommendations may be used by representatives of educational institutions and could be part of the preparation for future potential crises and significantly contribute to improving management by developing effective communication skills.

Key words: communication, management, pre-university.

Introduction

All the changes that take place at the level of societies at political, social and economic level and the way they are reflected influence the activity of the educational institutions. Thus, they need to reconsider themselves from an institutional and organizational perspective, adopting a different approach, with greater openness and transparency towards civil society and partners.

The school is an open evolving system - a dynamic environment in which different expectations and roles of educational actors meet. As a result, each educational institution must have a communication strategy, built on the objectives and responsibilities of the school, as an essential part of the overall strategy. External communication should not be the exclusive task of the manager. It should be the product of teamwork of all school staff. The reality reveals that, at the level of pre-university education institutions, there is no department of communications with the external public. Therefore, this task is taken over by the principal, in the vast majority of cases, or by one of the teachers, usually a board member, who has basic communication skills.

In the context of the pandemic, the process of external communication at the level of the pre-university education system has been subjected to a new wave of challenges that, in fact, the whole society has faced. Under these conditions, educational institutions have had to resort to communication media that were not formalized before. Their potential has now been proven, and schools have taken advantage of these means of communication in order to keep in touch with students, their families or the community. In what concerns communication with the coordinating institutions, the already used communication channels were kept, to which the mass media were added.

Communication during the crisis was the most important role of the manager, through which he “guides people and helps them stay united” (Petriglieri, 2020). Marsen (2020) noted that crisis communication must address both crisis management during the crisis and reputation management after the crisis. Fernandez and Shaw (2020) recommended that academic leaders focus on best practices, try to see opportunities in crisis, communicate clearly, connect with others.

Following these events, the importance of a strategic plan for the communication process was highlighted together with the existence of a communication map to support the educational process, ensuring its continuity and eliminating most of the disruptive factors.

Methodology

Through the methodology used, this research achieves the theoretical foundation of external communication within educational institutions, starting from the hypothesis that there are aspects related to organizational communication that can be improved in order to increase their performance.

Researchers E. Rogers and R. Agarwala-Rogers (1980) consider communication as the fundamental process leading to the harmonization of an institution. Communication is the tool that has the role of relationship, institutional integration, control and coordination, adaptation of the organization to the external environment.

The research is based on three functions of communication that were subjected to this analysis: the function of regulating basic activities, the function of maintaining organizational communication and the function of innovation of organizational communication.

The regulatory function of the basic communication activities refers to the institutional organization and includes the instructions, procedures, reports developed to solve the organization's problems related to the communication process. The efficiency of the use of the regulatory function of the basic activities regarding communication is reflected in the smooth running of the activities specific to the organization and in ensuring the conditions necessary to increase the performance of school organizations.

The function of maintaining organizational communication has the mission of ensuring the functioning conditions of organizations in the relationship with the family and the community. This is manifested through the establishment of rules and policies of organizations.

The innovation function of organizational communication is extremely important to establish the school's long-term vision and strengthen the school's position in a highly challenging educational market.

The innovation function of organizational communication requires the institution to be open to the suggestions made by direct and indirect beneficiaries, the family and the community, and to put into practice the ideas that can contribute to increasing the performance of the communication process.

The general objective established was to identify the deficiencies of the communication process at the school level, with an impact on external communication.

The research sought to formulate some value judgments on the teachers' perception of the predominant functions of external communication at the level of pre-university educational institutions. Two specific objectives were derived from this objective:

SO.1 Knowing the teachers' perception about the predominant functions of external communication at the level of pre-university education institutions and

SO.2 Knowing the teachers' perception regarding the elements of external communication at the level of pre-university education institutions.

The instrument used was the questionnaire, structured on items with answers on a Likert scale, ranging from one to five, where number 1 represents "Total Disagreement" and number 5 represents "Total Agreement".

Internal consistency testing related to the considered variables was carried out using the Cronbach Alpha coefficient (Jaba & Grama, 2004). This set of variables is characterized by a Cronbach's Alpha factor value of 0.982.

Findings

The items were constructed in the form of statements with the help of which it is possible to quantify the importance given by teaching staff to the predominant functions of external communication at the level of pre-university educational institutions.

The items captured aspects related to:

- the quality of messages used in communication within the school-family-community relationship includes the characteristics of an effective message: clarity, coherence and completeness;
- the types of message transmission channels and whether new technologies are used to make information transmission time more efficient;
- the presence of feed-back in formal communication within the school-family-community relationship;
- message encoding/decoding activity; the ease with which the messages received by the school organization from the family and community are understood;
- the availability of sending/receiving messages by the school, family and community, in their capacity as the main subjects of communication, active during the act of transmitting/receiving information;
- formulating comprehensible messages for receivers;
- the environment provided by school organizations, favorable for communication within the school-family-community relationship and oriented towards the exchange of information;
- the school management support of the formation of an environment oriented towards the exchange of information;
- the efficiency of the communication channels used.

The responses were paired for analysis with the SPSS program.

The analysis showed that, at the level of communication functions, there are aspects that can be improved, especially in the function of maintaining organizational communication and the function of innovating organizational communication. Better results were obtained in the communication regulation function, being able to conclude that the school establishes its communication relationship with its partners at a formal level.

Another conclusion is that teachers are not specially prepared for the field of communication by the school through training programs. The respondents believe that, at the school level, there is an openness for external communication with the family and the community. On the other hand, the preference for the managers' formal side of communication with the family and the community was highlighted, although informal communication predominates at the school level.

Discussion and conclusions

During the pandemic, when the school was unprepared for such a situation, the school management was put to a test. Research carried out by specialists in education sciences from the University of Bucharest showed that teachers had to manage the situation without being supported (neither morally, nor materially). The differences between the two environments (urban/rural) deepened, the material aspect of the impossibility of investing in the technology to ensure the continuation of the educational process had undesired consequences. The function of maintaining communication was the one that did not work in optimal parameters, and the one of innovation needed financial support for the implementation of technologies. Managers now had an important role by involving the community in

supporting schools, and where this was achieved, schools received the necessary support much more quickly than from the coordinating institutions.

The pandemic crisis highlighted the importance of communication, and the reports that followed concluded that a rethinking of the communication strategy was needed. Thus, in the OECD guidelines, instructions are provided for the development of medium-term education strategies and, more broadly, for the contribution to strengthening the resilience of school systems for potential educational emergencies (OECD, 2020)

Broad communication of the implementation strategy provides clarity to all policy stakeholders about several central elements: the objectives, what needs to be done and

how different people can be involved to achieve them, the type of data that can help understand progress towards goals, and the timing and extent of action to be taken.

The OECD proposes four major directions of action for educational institutions, through which they can more easily manage crisis situations such as COVID 19. Analyzing these directions of action, one can see the importance of correct and coherent school communication with higher institutions, family and community.

The second direction is focused on the involvement of all interested parties in solving the crisis situation. The four proposed action steps assume types of communication initiated by the school and directed towards the interested parties, as can be seen in the figure 1.

Figure 1 - The Education strategy - (adaptation according to OECD, 2020)

The first step is to build policies following a consultation process with key representatives such as trade unions, school principals, parents' associations, education and health specialists, through which to outline a solution adapted to the reality of the stakeholders. The second step refers to the involvement of all interested parties in the education process, which must be managed by the school, but also

supported by policies developed by higher fora, especially in areas such as health and safety. An important step, which fortunately has started to be implemented here, is building a system to maintain contact with partners, through existing communication platforms (applications, school portal, newsletters, etc.). A final step is the continuous modeling of the school's response according to the feedback of the interested parties, which involves maintaining communication, requesting periodic responses from partners with the aim of adapting existing strategies to their needs.

Teachers received help from:

Figure 2 – Support received by teachers during the COVID-19 (adaptation according to University of Bucharest - 2021)

One of the conclusions we reached emphasizes the importance of family and community involvement, which can be achieved through clear and effective communication. Harris and Jones (2020) shared the same idea, arguing that “creating stronger links with parent/community groups to support families, youth and children is now a necessity to deal with the many challenges that COVID19 has created.” As shown in figure 2, community and family involvement were very low in Romania during the pandemic.

Although the majority of teaching staff showed interest in direct communication with quick and lasting effects, in times of crisis indirect communication is welcome and the current technique manages to keep the school connected with the family and the community. As a result, in many schools, various activities (sessions, classes, meetings, etc.) continued to take place online, although not frequently. The pandemic has forced educational institutions to take a big step towards technology. The Ministry of Education and many other institutions in the community have invested in connecting schools to the Internet, in equipping them with specific devices. Apart from this, teachers had to invest in their professional training in order to be able to use the platforms and programs necessary to carry out their activity. Families have begun to discover the advantages of using digital catalogs, a project also supported by the Ministry of Education and currently running only in pilot schools.

Clearly, the field of communication has undergone important changes at the level of educational institutions, which forces them to adopt a new communication strategy, adapted to new needs.

Considering all these aspects, we can extract the following recommendations:

- The need to draw up a communication map at the level of educational institutions;
- Management improvement by developing the school principals' communication skills;
- Clear and effective communication maintenance with the family and community, which will result in more prompt involvement in solving school problems during a crisis.

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